

COMPARATIVE BOOK APPRAISAL FOR ACADEMIC UTILIZATION

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Abstract:

Critical evaluation of teaching-learning materials is a fundamental component of the educative process in schools. The need to evaluate information contained in school books is beyond question. Academic success for both teachers and students partly depends on such appraisal. Sensing this tremendous importance, the English Language Centre (ELC) of Ibra College of Technology (ICT) conducted an evaluation of its Project and Presentation Book, comparing it with that of Higher College of Technology (HCT). Using a prepared survey questionnaire, the study drew the needed data from teacher participants, particularly those who teach the subject. Ratings for each descriptive statement then were tabularized and presented in the following pages. Indeed, similar materials at times could be best appraised via detailed comparison of their attributes.

Keywords: critical evaluation, project and presentation, comparison, academic utilization, learning materials

1. Introduction

Classroom materials, books in particular, need not be used hastily for teaching-learning ends. This is not to make light of their importance, now that books sales had been declining due to the advent of e-books (Curtis, 2011). Rather, it is to give way to necessary evaluation procedures prior to using them for classroom purposes. Textbooks in particular should then be appraised first to determine their accuracy, relevance, and effectiveness. This explains the conduct of this present study that subjected book materials to review.

A book review, which is akin to book assessment or appraisal, is a form of literary criticism wherein books are analyzed based on style, content, and merit (Princeton, 2011). A book review could be an opinion piece, summary review, or scholarly review. Books may be reviewed for periodicals such as magazines or

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newspapers, as school material, or for websites on the net. The review's length may vary, from a single paragraph to a lengthy essay. Or it may be based on given statements with commensurate percentage equivalents more or less similar to this study. Such a review may assess the book based on personal taste or institutional demands.

Educational assessment, being the broader umbrella covering materials evaluation such as books, is the systematic process that documents and uses empirical data on skill, knowledge, beliefs, and attitudes to refine programs and to improve students' learning (Allen, 2004). Data assessment may be obtained by directly examining works to determine learning outcomes, or based on data from which evaluators can draw inferences on learning (Kuh et. al, 2014). Assessment often resembles tests, but is not of course limited to a test. It may focus on individual learners, the learning community, a course (including its materials like books, academic programs, an institution, or the educational system in general as has been used since the Second World War (Nelson & Dawson, 2014).

2. Comparative evaluation

Under the so-called comparative education, a social science discipline, evaluation entails the scrutiny of various educational systems including the teaching-learning materials used, like those in different countries. Professionals in this field are advancing evocative terms and guidelines for global education, enhancing academic structures and providing contexts in which educational programs and academic initiatives, obviously like the production of books for classroom use, can be assessed (Bray, 1995). Through the years, researchers in this field have focused on comparisons within one country over time. Still, large-scale projects like the PISA or TIMSS studies have made significant findings via explicitly comparative macro-analysis of massive sets of data. Recent samples of this include studies that analyze intra-European, and intra-American teacher education (Sabrin, 2018).

Evaluation—as a systematic determination of a book's merit, worth, and significance—uses criteria that are governed by a set of standards. It is often used to appraise and characterize subjects of interest within the wide range of education. It can assist a project to assess an aim, a concept/proposal, or an alternative for decision-making; or to ascertain achievement in regard to objectives and results of any completed action (Staff, 1995). Primary, besides gaining insights into existing initiatives, evaluation provides reflection and assistance in identifying future changes (Tufo, 2002).

Comparative or otherwise, evaluation interprets and gives meaning to predictions, or actual impacts of proposals/results. It looks closely at original objectives, predictions, and accomplishments. It can be formative, taking place during a project's development, with the intent of improving the value/effectiveness of the project. It can likewise be summative, drawing lessons from the completed project later (Scriven, 1967). Evaluation, then, is a systematic, meticulous application of scientific methods in

assessing the design, implementation, and outcomes of a project (Ross et. al, 2004) such as the books in this particular study.

3. How it's done

This study stems from Ibra College of Technology's evaluation of its Project and Presentation Book, comparing it with that of Higher College of Technology. Using a prepared survey questionnaire, the study drew the needed data from teacher participants, particularly those who teach the subject. Ratings for each descriptive statement were tabularized and presented in the succeeding pages.

The paper uses the content analysis approach, focusing on the contents of books for purposes of describing and drawing comparisons about the materials. With quasi-evaluation approach, content analysis judgments need not be based on value statements. They can be based on knowledge. Such content analyses are not evaluations, but when based on values, they are. The study further allows, as a key strength, for unobtrusive analysis of structured materials. Samples may be unrepresentative, yet they overwhelm in volume. Analysis designs are often overly simplistic for question.

4. Results

General Attributes – Detailed Comparative

Respondents' #	A		B		C		D		E		F		G		H		I	
	ICT	HCT	ICT	HCT	ICT	HCT	ICT	HCT	ICT	HCT	ICT	HCT	ICT	HCT	ICT	HCT	ICT	HCT
1	4	3	3	3	3	1	4	1	4	3	4	3	3	2	4	3	3	3
2	3	3	2	3	3	2	4	2	3	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	2	2
3	4	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	3	3	2	3	2	3	2	3	1	3
4	3	3	2	3	3	2	3	2	3	2	3	3	3	2	2	2	3	2
5	3	2	4	2	4	1	3	1	3	2	3	3	4	2	4	3	3	2
6	4	3	2	3	2	4	2	2	3	4	3	2	3	2	2	3	2	4
7	4	0	4	4	1	4	1	4	1	4	1	4	2	4	3	4	1	4
8	2	3	1	2	0	2	1	1	1	2	2	3	2	2	3	2	2	2
9	2	3	2	3	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	4	2	1
10	3	4	2	3	1	3	2	4	2	4	2	4	1	4	2	3	1	4
11	2	4	1	3	1	2	1	3	1	3	3	4	2	3	1	4	1	3
12	3	4	3	3	4	2	4	3	3	3	3	4	4	3	3	4	3	4
13	2	3	2	3	1	3	2	2	2	3	2	3	2	2	3	2	3	3
14	3	2	3	2	2	0	3	0	4	1	4	1	3	2	2	1	3	1
15	3	3	2	4	1	2	1	2	2	4	2	4	1	2	1	3	1	4
16	4	3	4	2	4	2	4	2	4	2	4	2	4	2	4	3	4	3
17	3	4	3	4	1	3	1	3	1	3	3	3	2	3	3	4	1	4
18	4	4	4	4	3	4	3	4	3	4	4	4	3	4	3	4	0	4
19	1	3	2	4	2	3	2	3	2	3	2	4	0	4	0	3	1	4
20	2	4	2	4	2	3	2	3	2	3	2	3	2	3	2	1	2	2
21	2	3	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	3	3	2	3
22	4	4	4	4	4	2	3	2	3	3	3	2	3	3	4	3	3	3
23	1	4	1	3	2	2	2	1	0	2	2	1	4	2	4	4	0	4
Mean	2.87	3.13	2.52	3.09	2.13	2.26	2.30	2.17	2.35	2.74	2.52	3.00	2.30	2.65	2.48	3.04	1.87	3.00
Diff-M	0.26		0.57		0.13		-0.13		0.39		0.48		0.35		0.57		1.13	

Legend:

ICT – Ibra College of Technology, HCT – Higher College of Technology, Diff-M – Mean Difference

A - It matches with the learning outcomes of the course., **B** - It can be exploited fully using the recommended teaching methodologies., **C** - It is compatible with the background knowledge of the students., **D** - It is well-matched with the level of the students., **E** - It is attuned with the needs of the learners., **F** - Its layout is appropriate., **G** - It indicates efficient use of text and visuals., **H** - Its printing quality is high., **I** - The material is up-to-date.

A. It matches with the learning outcomes of the course.

Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Diff (T2 - T1)	Dev (Diff - M)	Sq. Dev
4	3	-1	-1.26	1.59
3	3	0	-0.26	0.07
4	3	-1	-1.26	1.59
3	3	0	-0.26	0.07
3	2	-1	-1.26	1.59
4	3	-1	-1.26	1.59
4	0	-4	-4.26	18.16
2	3	1	0.74	0.55
2	3	1	0.74	0.55
3	4	1	0.74	0.55
2	4	2	1.74	3.02
3	4	1	0.74	0.55
2	3	1	0.74	0.55
3	2	-1	-1.26	1.59
3	3	0	-0.26	0.07
4	3	-1	-1.26	1.59
3	4	1	0.74	0.55
4	4	0	-0.26	0.07
1	3	2	1.74	3.02
2	4	2	1.74	3.02
2	3	1	0.74	0.55
4	4	0	-0.26	0.07
1	4	3	2.74	7.50
		M: 0.26		S: 48.43

Significance Level:

0.01

0.05

0.10

One-tailed or two-tailed hypothesis?:

One-tailed

Two-tailed

Difference Scores Calculations

Mean: 0.26
 $\mu = 0$
 $S^2 = SS/df = 48.43/(23-1) = 2.20$
 $S^2_M = S^2/N = 2.20/23 = 0.10$
 $S_M = \sqrt{S^2_M} = \sqrt{0.10} = 0.31$

T-value Calculation

$t = (M - \mu)/S_M = (0.26 - 0)/0.31 = 0.84$

The value of t is 0.843179. The value of p is 0.408202. The result is *not* significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

B. It can be exploited fully using the recommended teaching methodologies.

Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Diff (T2 - T1)	Dev (Diff - M)	Sq. Dev
3	3	0	-0.57	0.32
2	3	1	0.43	0.19
3	3	0	-0.57	0.32
2	3	1	0.43	0.19
4	2	-2	-2.57	6.58
2	3	1	0.43	0.19
4	4	0	-0.57	0.32
1	2	1	0.43	0.19
2	3	1	0.43	0.19
2	3	1	0.43	0.19
1	3	2	1.43	2.06
3	3	0	-0.57	0.32
2	3	1	0.43	0.19
3	2	-1	-1.57	2.45
2	4	2	1.43	2.06
4	2	-2	-2.57	6.58
3	4	1	0.43	0.19
4	4	0	-0.57	0.32
2	4	2	1.43	2.06
2	4	2	1.43	2.06
2	2	0	-0.57	0.32
4	4	0	-0.57	0.32
1	3	2	1.43	2.06

M: 0.57 S: 29.65

Significance Level:

0.01

0.05

0.10

One-tailed or two-tailed hypothesis?:

One-tailed

Two-tailed

Difference Scores Calculations

Mean: 0.57
 $\mu = 0$
 $S^2 = SS/df = 29.65/(23-1) = 1.35$
 $S^2_M = S^2/N = 1.35/23 = 0.06$
 $S_M = \sqrt{S^2_M} = \sqrt{0.06} = 0.24$

T-value Calculation

$t = (M - \mu)/S_M = (0.57 - 0)/0.24 = 2.33$

The value of t is 2.334869. The value of p is 0.029077. The result is significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

C. It is compatible with the background knowledge of the students.

Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Diff (T2 - T1)	Dev (Diff - M)	Sq. Dev
3	1	-2	-2.13	4.54
3	2	-1	-1.13	1.28
2	2	0	-0.13	0.02
3	2	-1	-1.13	1.28
4	1	-3	-3.13	9.80
2	4	2	1.87	3.50
1	4	3	2.87	8.23
0	2	2	1.87	3.50
2	1	-1	-1.13	1.28
1	3	2	1.87	3.50
1	2	1	0.87	0.76
4	2	-2	-2.13	4.54
1	3	2	1.87	3.50
2	0	-2	-2.13	4.54
1	2	1	0.87	0.76
4	2	-2	-2.13	4.54
1	3	2	1.87	3.50
3	4	1	0.87	0.76
2	3	1	0.87	0.76
2	3	1	0.87	0.76
1	2	1	0.87	0.76
4	2	-2	-2.13	4.54
2	2	0	-0.13	0.02

M: 0.13 S: 66.61

Significance Level:

0.01

0.05

0.10

One-tailed or two-tailed hypothesis?:

One-tailed

Two-tailed

Difference Scores Calculations

Mean: 0.13
 $\mu = 0$
 $S^2 = SS/df = 66.61/(23-1) = 3.03$
 $S^2_M = S^2/N = 3.03/23 = 0.13$
 $S_M = \sqrt{S^2_M} = \sqrt{0.13} = 0.36$

T-value Calculation

$t = (M - \mu)/S_M = (0.13 - 0)/0.36 = 0.36$

The value of t is 0.359504. The value of p is 0.722646. The result is *not* significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

D. It is well-matched with the level of the students.

Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Diff (T2 - T1)	Dev (Diff - M)	Sq. Dev
4	1	-3	-2.87	8.23
4	2	-2	-1.87	3.50
2	2	0	0.13	0.02
3	2	-1	-0.87	0.76
3	1	-2	-1.87	3.50
2	2	0	0.13	0.02
1	4	3	3.13	9.80
1	1	0	0.13	0.02
2	1	-1	-0.87	0.76
2	4	2	2.13	4.54
1	3	2	2.13	4.54
4	3	-1	-0.87	0.76
2	2	0	0.13	0.02
3	0	-3	-2.87	8.23
1	2	1	1.13	1.28
4	2	-2	-1.87	3.50
1	3	2	2.13	4.54
3	4	1	1.13	1.28
2	3	1	1.13	1.28
2	3	1	1.13	1.28
1	2	1	1.13	1.28
3	2	-1	-0.87	0.76
2	1	-1	-0.87	0.76
		M: -0.13	S: 60.61	

Significance Level:

0.01
 0.05
 0.10

One-tailed or two-tailed hypothesis?:

One-tailed
 Two-tailed

Difference Scores Calculations

Mean: -0.13
 $\mu = 0$
 $S^2 = SS/df = 60.61/(23-1) = 2.75$
 $S^2_M = S^2/N = 2.75/23 = 0.12$
 $S_M = \sqrt{S^2_M} = \sqrt{0.12} = 0.35$

T-value Calculation

$t = (M - \mu)/S_M = (-0.13 - 0)/0.35 = -0.38$

The value of t is -0.376878. The value of p is 0.709875. The result is not significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

E. It is attuned with the needs of the learners.

Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Diff (T2 - T1)	Dev (Diff - M)	Sq. Dev
4	3	-1	-1.39	1.94
3	2	-1	-1.39	1.94
3	3	0	-0.39	0.15
3	2	-1	-1.39	1.94
3	2	-1	-1.39	1.94
3	4	1	0.61	0.37
1	4	3	2.61	6.81
1	2	1	0.61	0.37
2	1	-1	-1.39	1.94
2	4	2	1.61	2.59
1	3	2	1.61	2.59
3	3	0	-0.39	0.15
2	3	1	0.61	0.37
4	1	-3	-3.39	11.50
2	4	2	1.61	2.59
4	2	-2	-2.39	5.72
1	3	2	1.61	2.59
3	4	1	0.61	0.37
2	3	1	0.61	0.37
2	3	1	0.61	0.37
2	2	0	-0.39	0.15
3	3	0	-0.39	0.15
0	2	2	1.61	2.59
		M: 0.39	S: 49.48	

Significance Level:

0.01
 0.05
 0.10

One-tailed or two-tailed hypothesis?:

One-tailed
 Two-tailed

Difference Scores Calculations

Mean: 0.39
 $\mu = 0$
 $S^2 = SS/df = 49.48/(23-1) = 2.25$
 $S^2_M = S^2/N = 2.25/23 = 0.10$
 $S_M = \sqrt{S^2_M} = \sqrt{0.10} = 0.31$

T-value Calculation

$t = (M - \mu)/S_M = (0.39 - 0)/0.31 = 1.25$

The value of t is 1.251361. The value of p is 0.223946. The result is not significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

F. Its layout is appropriate.

Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Diff (T2 - T1)	Dev (Diff - M)	Sq. Dev
4	3	-1	-1.48	2.19
2	2	0	-0.48	0.23
2	3	1	0.52	0.27
3	3	0	-0.48	0.23
3	3	0	-0.48	0.23
3	2	-1	-1.48	2.19
1	4	3	2.52	6.36
2	3	1	0.52	0.27
2	2	0	-0.48	0.23
2	4	2	1.52	2.32
3	4	1	0.52	0.27
3	4	1	0.52	0.27
2	3	1	0.52	0.27
4	1	-3	-3.48	12.10
2	4	2	1.52	2.32
4	2	-2	-2.48	6.14
3	3	0	-0.48	0.23
4	4	0	-0.48	0.23
2	4	2	1.52	2.32
2	3	1	0.52	0.27
1	2	1	0.52	0.27
3	2	-1	-1.48	2.19
1	4	3	2.52	6.36
		M: 0.48		S: 47.74

Significance Level:

0.01

0.05

0.10

One-tailed or two-tailed hypothesis?:

One-tailed

Two-tailed

Difference Scores Calculations

Mean: 0.48
 $\mu = 0$
 $S^2 = SS/df = 47.74/(23-1) = 2.17$
 $S^2_M = S^2/N = 2.17/23 = 0.09$
 $S_M = \sqrt{S^2_M} = \sqrt{0.09} = 0.31$

T-value Calculation

$t = (M - \mu)/S_M = (0.48 - 0)/0.31 = 1.56$

The value of t is 1.557051. The value of p is 0.133728. The result is *not* significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

G. It indicates efficient use of text and visuals.

Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Diff (T2 - T1)	Dev (Diff - M)	Sq. Dev
3	2	-1	-1.35	1.82
2	2	0	-0.35	0.12
2	3	1	0.65	0.43
3	2	-1	-1.35	1.82
4	2	-2	-2.35	5.51
2	2	0	-0.35	0.12
3	4	1	0.65	0.43
2	2	0	-0.35	0.12
2	1	-1	-1.35	1.82
1	4	3	2.65	7.03
2	3	1	0.65	0.43
4	3	-1	-1.35	1.82
2	2	0	-0.35	0.12
3	2	-1	-1.35	1.82
1	2	1	0.65	0.43
4	2	-2	-2.35	5.51
2	3	1	0.65	0.43
3	4	1	0.65	0.43
0	4	4	3.65	13.34
2	3	1	0.65	0.43
1	2	1	0.65	0.43
3	3	0	-0.35	0.12
2	4	2	1.65	2.73
		M: 0.35		S: 51.22

Significance Level:

0.01

0.05

0.10

One-tailed or two-tailed hypothesis?:

One-tailed

Two-tailed

Difference Scores Calculations

Mean: 0.35
 $\mu = 0$
 $S^2 = SS/df = 51.22/(23-1) = 2.33$
 $S^2_M = S^2/N = 2.33/23 = 0.10$
 $S_M = \sqrt{S^2_M} = \sqrt{0.10} = 0.32$

T-value Calculation

$t = (M - \mu)/S_M = (0.35 - 0)/0.32 = 1.09$

The value of t is 1.093273. The value of p is 0.286101. The result is *not* significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

H. Its printing quality is high.

Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Diff (T2 - T1)	Dev (Diff - M)	Sq. Dev
4	3	-1	-1.57	2.45
3	3	0	-0.57	0.32
2	3	1	0.43	0.19
2	2	0	-0.57	0.32
4	3	-1	-1.57	2.45
2	3	1	0.43	0.19
3	4	1	0.43	0.19
3	2	-1	-1.57	2.45
2	4	2	1.43	2.06
2	3	1	0.43	0.19
1	4	3	2.43	5.93
3	4	1	0.43	0.19
2	3	1	0.43	0.19
2	1	-1	-1.57	2.45
1	3	2	1.43	2.06
4	3	-1	-1.57	2.45
3	4	1	0.43	0.19
3	4	1	0.43	0.19
0	3	3	2.43	5.93
2	1	-1	-1.57	2.45
3	3	0	-0.57	0.32
4	3	-1	-1.57	2.45
2	4	2	1.43	2.06
		M: 0.57	S: 37.65	

Significance Level:

0.01

0.05

0.10

One-tailed or two-tailed hypothesis?:

One-tailed

Two-tailed

Difference Scores Calculations

Mean: 0.57
 $\mu = 0$
 $S^2 = SS/df = 37.65/(23-1) = 1.71$
 $S^2_M = S^2/N = 1.71/23 = 0.07$
 $S_M = \sqrt{S^2_M} = \sqrt{0.07} = 0.27$

T-value Calculation

$t = (M - \mu)/S_M = (0.57 - 0)/0.27 = 2.07$

The value of t is 2.072029. The value of p is 0.050187. The result is *not* significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

I. The material is up-to-date.

Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Diff (T2 - T1)	Dev (Diff - M)	Sq. Dev
3	3	0	-1.13	1.28
2	2	0	-1.13	1.28
1	3	2	0.87	0.76
3	2	-1	-2.13	4.54
3	2	-1	-2.13	4.54
2	4	2	0.87	0.76
1	4	3	1.87	3.50
2	2	0	-1.13	1.28
2	1	-1	-2.13	4.54
1	4	3	1.87	3.50
1	3	2	0.87	0.76
3	4	1	-0.13	0.02
2	3	1	-0.13	0.02
3	1	-2	-3.13	9.80
1	4	3	1.87	3.50
4	3	-1	-2.13	4.54
1	4	3	1.87	3.50
0	4	4	2.87	8.23
1	4	3	1.87	3.50
2	2	0	-1.13	1.28
2	3	1	-0.13	0.02
3	3	0	-1.13	1.28
0	4	4	2.87	8.23
		M: 1.13	S: 70.61	

Significance Level:

0.01

0.05

0.10

One-tailed or two-tailed hypothesis?:

One-tailed

Two-tailed

Difference Scores Calculations

Mean: 1.13
 $\mu = 0$
 $S^2 = SS/df = 70.61/(23-1) = 3.21$
 $S^2_M = S^2/N = 3.21/23 = 0.14$
 $S_M = \sqrt{S^2_M} = \sqrt{0.14} = 0.37$

T-value Calculation

$t = (M - \mu)/S_M = (1.13 - 0)/0.37 = 3.03$

The value of t is 3.026159. The value of p is 0.006206. The result is significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

Criteria	ICT-ELC Mean Score	Interpretation	HCT-ELC Mean Score	Interpretation	Mean Score Difference HCT - ICT
A	2.87	ST	3.13	OT	0.26
B	2.52	ST	3.09	OT	0.57
C	2.13	ST	2.26	ST	0.13
D	2.30	ST	2.17	ST	-0.13
E	2.35	ST	2.70	ST	0.35
F	2.52	ST	3.00	OT	0.48
G	2.30	ST	2.66	ST	0.36
H	2.48	ST	3.04	OT	0.56
I	1.87	RT	2.00	ST	1.13
Overall Mean Score	2.37	ST	2.78	ST	0.41

Legend:

NT – Never True, RT – Rarely True, ST – Sometimes True, OT – Often True, AT – Always True

A - It matches with the learning outcomes of the course., B - It can be exploited fully using the recommended teaching methodologies., C - It is compatible with the background knowledge of the students., D - It is well-matched with the level of the students., E - It is attuned with the needs of the learners., F - Its layout is appropriate., G - It indicates efficient use of text and visuals., H - Its printing quality is high., I - The material is up-to-date.

A. HCT and ICT Means of the General Attributes
– Overall Comparative using a T-Test

Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Diff (T2 - T1)	Dev (Diff - M)	Sq. Dev
2.87	3.13	0.26	-0.04	0.00
2.52	3.09	0.57	0.27	0.07
2.13	2.26	0.13	-0.17	0.03
2.30	2.17	-0.13	-0.43	0.19
2.35	2.70	0.35	0.05	0.00
2.52	3.00	0.48	0.18	0.03
2.30	2.66	0.36	0.06	0.00
2.48	3.04	0.56	0.26	0.07
1.87	2.00	0.13	-0.17	0.03
		M: 0.30		S: 0.42

Significance Level:

0.01

0.05

0.10

One-tailed or two-tailed hypothesis?:

One-tailed

Two-tailed

Difference Scores Calculations

Mean: 0.30
 $\mu = 0$
 $S^2 = SS/df = 0.42/(9-1) = 0.05$
 $S^2_M = S^2/N = 0.05/9 = 0.01$
 $S_M = \sqrt{S^2_M} = \sqrt{0.01} = 0.08$

T-value Calculation

$t = (M - \mu)/S_M = (0.30 - 0)/0.08 = 3.93$

The value of t is 3.927124. The value of p is 0.004374. The result is significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

B. HCT and ICT Means of the General Attributes – Overall Comparative using a Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test

Test Statistics^a

	HCT_A - ICT_A	HCT_B - ICT_B	HCT_C - ICT_C	HCT_D - ICT_D	HCT_E - ICT_E	HCT_F - ICT_F	HCT_G - ICT_G	HCT_H - ICT_H	HCT_I - ICT_I
Z	-1.162 ^b	-1.972^b	-.267 ^b	-.370 ^c	-1.322 ^b	-1.530 ^b	-.921 ^b	-1.927 ^b	-2.640^b
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.245	.049	.790	.711	.186	.126	.357	.054	.008

a. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test

b. Based on negative ranks. c. Based on positive ranks.

* Those in blue color exhibit significant difference.

(same TWO CRITERIA WHERE THE DIFFERENCE LIES as revealed in the dependent t-test)

5. Discussion

In this study, descriptive attributes of the books are given, and serve as options for the participants to choose from. Their truism may be questioned by some. However, it should be noted that the focus, or what this study is after, is the result of comparison rather than whether the attributes are true or not. Strict adherence to sets of methodological assumptions could make evaluation more acceptable to mainstream audiences, but such adherence may work towards preventing the evaluators from developing newer strategies in dealing with problems that projects face.

It is said that, no matter how clear the results are as exemplified by the above tables, only few of evaluation reports are utilized. One justification for this is that, when evaluation findings are eventually challenged, or utilization failed, it was because stakeholders/clients found the inferences weak, the warrants less convincing. Some reasons behind this may be the evaluator's failure to establish sets of shared aims, or perhaps overly ambitious aims are created, failing to compromise and incorporate differences within the evaluation aims and processes.

None of such problems are due to the scarcity of evaluation definition, but are rather due to the evaluators that attempt to impose pre-disposed notions, and definitions of evaluation on projects. The main reason for poor usage of evaluation is, arguably, due to the failure of tailoring of evaluation to suit the clients' needs, due to a pre-defined idea of what evaluation is, rather than what the clients' needs are.

The development of comparative evaluation, as suggested by this simple study, will require arriving at some applicable ways of asking-and-stating the results of questions on the project at hand.

6. Conclusion

It is concluded that projects, evaluators, and stakeholders (to include funders) may all have potentially different views on how best to evaluate projects since each could have a varying definition of 'merit'. Thus, the core of the problem, is defining what is of great

value. From such perspective, evaluation becomes a contested term, as evaluators use the term 'evaluation' to describe assessment, or investigation of a project whilst others merely perceive evaluation as something similar with applied research. At any rate, subjecting teaching-learning materials to evaluation still pays off.

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